

सत्यमेव जयते

Office of the Controller General of Patents, Designs & Trade Marks
Department of Industrial Policy & Promotion,
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Government of India

**INTELLECTUAL
PROPERTY INDIA**
PATENTS | DESIGNS | TRADE MARKS
GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS

Application Details

APPLICATION NUMBER	202341013781
APPLICATION TYPE	ORDINARY APPLICATION
DATE OF FILING	01/03/2023
APPLICANT NAME	PROF. Dr. KRISHNA KUMAR TP
TITLE OF INVENTION	MODELLING CUSTOMER DEMAND IN EBUSINESS PLATFORM THROUGH IMPROVED TECHNIQUES
FIELD OF INVENTION	COMPUTER SCIENCE
E-MAIL (As Per Record)	
ADDITIONAL-EMAIL (As Per Record)	tpk683@gmail.com
E-MAIL (UPDATED Online)	
PRIORITY DATE	
REQUEST FOR EXAMINATION DATE	--
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Application Status